

NIS 2 in Orbit: Cyber Challenges and Risk Management in Space

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of space-based services has introduced significant cybersecurity challenges. Satellites support essential services such as communications, navigation, and Earth observation, making them prime targets for cyber threats. Building upon the foundational analysis presented in the ENISA "Space Threat Landscape", this paper examines the evolving threat landscape dynamics of the space domain, taking into account the entire lifecycle of satellite systems—from design and development to decommissioning—while considering a comprehensive taxonomy of assets. The threat landscape constructed through an analysis of historical cyber incidents, highlights key threats and proves an assessment of the major threat actors operating within the domain. The paper introduces an interactive tool designed to offer clear and actionable recommendations for securing space systems. This tool leverages a comprehensive analysis of 281 controls, drawn from 13 frameworks, and maps them to each phase of the satellite lifecycle. Additionally, the paper underscores the importance of international cooperation and adherence to cybersecurity standards and regulatory frameworks, such as the NIS 2 Directive, to safeguard the space sector.

Keywords

Cybersecurity, ENISA, Space threat landscape, Risks, Controls, NIS 2

1. Introduction

As satellites are essential for global communications, navigation, and a wide spectrum of critical services, the economic and societal impact of a cybersecurity incident disrupting their operation makes (cyber)security a critical concern. As a matter of fact, Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union¹, (NIS2 Directive) recognizes the space

sector as a sector of high criticality, underscoring the need for robust cybersecurity measures to protect this critical ecosystem².

Satellite navigation systems like GPS (USA), GLONASS (Russia), BeiDou (China), and Galileo (EU), constitute the backbone of modern life as they play a crucial role in the delivery of a wide range of applications, from geolocation and emergency response to scientific research. However, their widespread use makes them attractive targets for cyber-attacks causing the disruption of critical services [3].

While navigation satellites are essential for geo-positioning, another crucial type of satellites is the communications satellites used for internet access, broadcasting, and global connectivity. Companies like SpaceX (Starlink), OneWeb, Iridium, and GlobalStar are revolutionizing global internet access, especially for remote areas, operating in total over 8,000 satellites in orbit, making cybersecurity critical to preventing data interception, signal disruption, and unauthorized access. Furthermore, earth observation satellites provide crucial data on weather, climate, and environmental monitoring, supporting disaster response and resource management. With nearly 600 active satellites dedicated to Earth observation, establishing secure communication channels and preventing data manipulation is vital to ensure accurate and reliable information. Space observation satellites are used for monitoring deep-space phenomena and measuring cosmic events. Despite their direct impact on daily life being less, securing their operation and data ensures the integrity of astronomical research.

The current surge in satellite launches is mainly driven by private companies and marks a new space race, resulting to over 75 countries operating satellites nowadays. Commercial reports postulate an ever-increasing reliance on space applications, predicting 38,000 additional satellites to be built and launched by 2033, 52 Exabytes of data traffic passing through satellites by 2029, and a \$1.7 trillion market revenue for space industry by 2032³. While this fosters innovation, it also introduces risks. A 2022 report from

¹ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148

(NIS 2 Directive). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32022L2555>

² NIS 2 Directive considers under the Space sector: "Operators of ground-based infrastructure, owned, managed and operated by Member States or by private parties that support the provision of space-based services, excluding providers of public electronic communications networks."

³ Cloud Computing via Satellite report (source: Northern Sky Research)

Northern Sky research⁴ highlights the growing cyberthreats to space-based assets and ground infrastructure. The rapid proliferation of commercial satellites, particularly small, inexpensive, and rapidly deployable ones, exacerbates cyber risks.

FIGURE 1 - SPACE LIFECYCLE

Undoubtedly, the space sector's rapid growth brings immense opportunities, but also significant cybersecurity challenges. This requires a fundamental shift in mindset, moving away from the assumption that the physical inaccessibility of satellite systems provides inherent security and, in general, security exceptionalism and security by obscurity. Instead, we must prioritize cybersecurity from the design phase and throughout the entire lifecycle, recognizing that vulnerabilities in satellite infrastructures could have far-reaching consequences for global security and connectivity. This involves adopting long-established cybersecurity practices, such as security by design, privacy by design, zero-trust architectures, robust supply chain security, secure coding practices, and cryptographic agility.

To this end, this paper builds upon of the foundational analysis presented in the ENISA "Space Threat Landscape" [1] leveraging its insights to explore the evolving threats and threat actors within the space domain, with respect to a structured analysis of lifecycle phases of satellites. Using the "Space Threat Landscape" as our "launch platform", this work underscores the urgent need for tool-aided risk management in space operation and emphasizes the importance of adhering to robust cybersecurity standards. In response to these challenges, we introduce an interactive mapping tool [13] designed to facilitate the implementation of security controls, along with the control dataset, for easy consumption through GRC tools. This tool is the result of a systematic analysis of 13 prominent risk management frameworks, tailored to address the unique complexities of space systems. Furthermore, we position the NIS 2 Directive as a main driving force for enhancing risk and incident management practices, as well as fostering greater cooperation among stakeholders in space operations. By integrating these elements, this paper aims to contribute to a more secure and resilient space ecosystem.

2. Space Ecosystem Lifecycle

Towards identifying the challenges and threats of an ecosystem, it is vital to first identify all phases that comprise its lifecycle so as to follow a systematic and structured

analysis approach. Various satellite lifecycle models are employed by prominent organisations governing the space sector and cybersecurity. However, despite variations in the ways in which actions are grouped into phases or the terminology employed, at their core these lifecycles remain the same, regardless of the ownership or intended use of the satellite systems, and whether they are commercial, military, or state-owned. Well-known satellite operation lifecycle models [12] are those of ESA [8], NASA [7], and JAXA [9], while BSI[10] and NIST[11] are similarly phased lifecycle models but with particular focus on cybersecurity aspects of operations. ENISA in [1], follows a unified perspective for the lifecycle model (see FIGURE 1) that allows easy mapping to the aforementioned models. With this unified model as a frame and search space analysts can systematically analyse the threat landscape of space domain and highlight the hostile actions and threat actors that can potentially appear in each phase.

Phase 1 – Design and Development phase focuses on defining requirements and mission goals and objectives. Apart from mission concepts, system-level requirements, and technology needs, security requirements shall be incorporated into the technical documentation for satellite components. Thus, security must be integrated from the start and be ensured, through rigorous testing and controls, throughout the entire lifecycle.

Phase 2 - Assembly phase involves integrating spacecraft components, including hardware and software assets for satellite operations. Supply chain cybersecurity and risk mitigation measures are crucial, requiring validation through tests and compliance audits for SW/HW used in the assembly. While SW modifications may be possible after the mission launch, hardware changes are limited.

Phase 3 – Pre-launch phase focuses on testing satellite functionality and establishing connectivity with ground control. Cybersecurity is crucial as it involves the secure integration, validation, and verification (IVV), of the satellite with the launch vehicle, infrastructure, operations centre and all the supporting and operational systems, while verifying hardware, software, and human interactions.

Phase 4 – Launch phase sends the space system to its operational environment and involves several safety and security-sensitive steps. Due to high costs and complexities, this phase is often outsourced. Cyber threats can target launch devices, installations and safety systems, requiring

⁴ Northern Sky Research. 2022. Space Cybersecurity: Current State and Future Needs. White Paper. April. www.nsr.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/NSR-Space-Cybersecurity-White-Paper-FINAL.pdf.

robust cybersecurity measures, while outsourcing also introduces supply chain risks.

Phase 5 – In-orbit testing takes place to verify systems' operational integrity. This phase includes the steps of injecting the satellite to transfer orbit and transfer of custody to the customer. Cybersecurity is crucial to ensure operational integrity of systems and ensure that there are no opportunities for malicious actors to exploit vulnerabilities during the transfer of custody.

Phase 6 – Operations phase involves mission-specific functions like data acquisition, processing, and communication, managed via ground stations. Cybersecurity is essential to protect sensitive data, communication, system integrity and secure firmware/software updates.

Phase 7 - Decommissioning is a high-risk process involving disposition of satellites and space structures. During this phase there are considerations for the secure handling and disposal of sensitive data, including intellectual property. Cybersecurity risks include data loss, unauthorized access, and potential hijacking of decommissioned satellites.

3. Asset Taxonomy and Domain Segmentation

For defining an assets' taxonomy for space landscape, one needs to look on the Ground, in Space and also consider the end users of services and the human resources that underpin the operational aspects of satellites throughout their lifecycle.

The ground segment includes the terrestrial systems that facilitate communication, monitoring of satellite activities, and relaying of essential telemetry data, as well as ground physical facilities. In fact, one needs to consider the assets that play a crucial role during the lifecycle of satellites on the ground, considering the union of the *Production, Transportation, Launch* and *Operation* phases.

The Space segment contains satellite(s) orbiting the Earth, either in the form of constellations or under arbitrary synergies in the context of specific missions and services. The assets comprising the space segment stem from two categories: *Satellite Operations (BUS)*, including all assets required to operate and maintain a satellite in orbit (e.g., RTOS, Antennas, etc.), and *Mission Execution*, referring to assets needed to fulfil the mission (e.g., payload data handling system). Although, mission execution assets may rely on BUS assets there is an increasing trend for keeping these two systems separated to serve distinct functions among different consumers.

The User segment contains interfaces and devices that enable end users to access and benefit from the services provided by a satellite, either through ground stations or the satellite directly. Thus, assets of the user segment fall into the categories of *Consumer interfaces*, such as Very-small-aperture terminals (VSATs) and antennas, and *Consumer*

endpoint devices (e.g., SAT phones and TV receivers, vehicles, etc.)

Finally, humans participating in development activities (Human Resources segment), supporting tasks and satellite operations, is an overarching aspect spanning across the entire lifecycle of satellites and segments, as they are inextricably linked to the security of mission-critical assets.

4. Space Threat Landscape

Understanding the threat landscape for satellite systems is crucial for safeguarding their operations and continuity of satellite-based services. This chapter delves into the web of threats and offers a threat taxonomy based on ENISA's work in [1].

I. Threats

In an effort to create a threat taxonomy, ENISA examined publicly known attacks against satellite systems as those collated by the Space Attacks Open Database Project⁵ covering the period between 1977 and 2019, alongside available information on more recent incidents included in ENISA Foresight Cybersecurity Threats for 2030⁶.

The majority of the space-based attacks took place on government and commercial targets. The majority of observed attacks took place between 2001 and 2010 (30 recorded attacks in total), with a slight reduction from 2011 to 2019. Prior to 2000, only 12 attacks had been identified. This list can be updated with an additional three major attacks in the space domain which took place by 2022. These attacks involved hijacking, jamming and Distributed Denial of Service and were primarily targeted the commercial satellite sector. Overall, Jamming was among the most frequent materialised threats targeting mainly Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), followed by hijacking and Computer Network Exploitation (CNE). Attacks aimed at control functions, as well as spoofing, eavesdropping and the employment of anti-satellite weapons (ASATs) were far less frequent during the observed period.

II. Threat Actors

By examining the incidents outlined in the previous paragraph, the threat actor taxonomy from ENISA's Threat Landscape [2] can be adapted to the space domain. The following threat actors have been identified as the most prominent within the domain:

State-nexus actors, rely on government resources to achieve their objectives. Primarily engaged in espionage and disruption, state-nexus actors are sometimes directed by the military, intelligence or state control apparatus of their

⁵ Space Security Community. Space Attacks Open Database Project. <https://www.spacesecurity.info/en/space-attacks-open-database/>

⁶ ENISA. 2023. ENISA Foresight Cybersecurity Threats for 2030. <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-foresight-cybersecurity-threats-for-2030>

country and often spend considerable time investigating their targets to identify weaknesses and entry points.

Cybercrime actors and hacker-for-hire actors, are primarily motivated by financial gain. Mainly targeting data or infrastructure, cybercrime actors often employ social engineering and either steal from their victims, engage in extortion, or aim to monetise the stolen information.

Private Sector Offensive Actors (PSOA), who are engaged in the cyber-surveillance industry. Focused on enabling other actors (e.g., governments, private individuals) to gain a competitive advantage against their peers, PSOAs specialise in developing and selling cyberweapons to their clients, equipping them with advanced cyber capabilities.

Hackers (a.k.a. Civil Activists), whose primary goal is to extract and expose data or disrupt business operations for ideological reasons or to draw attention to a specific cause.

Hackers, comprising a diverse set of malicious actors' subgroups that vary in their motivation, objectives, skillsets and capabilities. These may range from Cyberwarriors and Cyber Fighters to Blackhat hackers/Crackers.

Disgruntled Employees or Insider Attackers, who have detailed insight of the organisation and its systems. This includes staff, contractors, vendors, customers, or former employees.

Untrained/Reckless Employees, who may not have the intention to cause harm but may still do so as a result of negligence or insufficient training.

The above analysis highlights that threat actors, regardless of whether they utilise resources of their supporting organisation -if any-, can execute a wide range of attacks. That is, the profile of these attackers is a critical factor to consider as part of comprehensive risk assessment efforts.

III. Threat Taxonomy

Building upon the asset taxonomy, the following threat taxonomy focuses on applicable attacks against assets for which a direct cyber-relevant threat has been identified via a thorough analysis of academic and industrial resources for attacks applicable to the space domain as part of [1]. The taxonomy includes:

Nefarious Activity/Abuse (NAA): refer to intended actions that target ICT systems, infrastructure, and networks by means of malicious acts with the aim to either steal, alter, or destroy a specified target.

Eavesdropping/Interception/ Hijacking (EIH): actions aiming to listen, interrupt, or seize control of a third-party communication without consent.

Physical Attacks (PA): actions which aim to destroy, expose, alter, disable, steal or gain unauthorised access to physical assets such as infrastructure, hardware, or interconnection. While one could think that physical attacks

can happen only on the ground, interestingly, recent advancements make such attacks applicable also in space⁷.

Unintentional Damage (UD): unintentional actions causing destruction, harm, or injury of property or persons and results in a failure or reduction in usefulness. This is usually related with Untrained/Reckless Employees actors.

Failures or malfunctions (FM): partial or full insufficient functioning of an asset (hardware or software).

Outages (OUT): unexpected disruptions of service or decrease in quality falling below a required level.

Disaster (DIS): a sudden accident or a natural catastrophe that causes great damage or loss of life.

Legal (LEG): legal actions of third parties (contracting or otherwise), in order to prohibit actions or compensate for loss based on applicable law.

On top of the above, one needs to consider threats stemming from the use of legacy infrastructure and systems, which is a common case in the space domain, as well as the vulnerabilities that arise as result of the extended use of commercial off-the-shelf software (COTS) for different satellite components, as an aftermath of the intensive commercialisation of the domain.

5. Risks and Challenges

- So, what are the main risks and challenges identified then?

To answer this question, we examine the interplay between the lifecycle model, asset taxonomy, real-life incidents, and threat actors along with their motivations. In what follows, we present a set of risk cases worth highlighting due to their likelihood of occurrence and possible cascading effects.

Supply Chain Risk: the space sector is heavily dependent on vast global supply chains, introducing potential vulnerabilities that adversaries could exploit to compromise critical systems. The risk of supply chain intrusion is two pronged: software components are vulnerable to insertion, modification, or removal of information, and corruption of the code or functionality during development, upgrade, or update of the system; hardware components are susceptible to intentional or unintentional introduction of components or electronic chips containing defects, malware, or backdoors for system sabotage or espionage.

Use of Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) components: economy of scale leads to increasingly rely on off-the-shelf components for communication, launch, data reception, and control facilities. This poses a challenge as

⁷ Although innovations in [on-orbit servicing capabilities](#) might be rendering this restriction moot, e.g., China's Shijian-21 [Krebs, Gunter D. "SJ 21"; Gunter's Space Page. https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/sj-21.htm], and NASA's OSAM-I <https://www.nasa.gov/mission/on-orbit-servicing-assembly-and-manufacturing-1>

details components used in satellites and infrastructures are publicly available, easing malicious actors to familiarise themselves with the targeted systems.

Legacy Systems: given the nature and the location of the space systems, many space-based assets have been designed without the security considerations needed to foresee or mitigate some of the present-day cyber challenges. Their remote nature adds another layer of complexity, making necessary updates difficult and in some instances impossible, leaving vulnerabilities that render satellite systems susceptible to cyberattacks.

Limited Visibility: the remote nature of the space systems poses challenges in detecting and responding to cybersecurity incidents and addressing vulnerabilities. In contrast to legacy systems, modern satellites require regular updates through remote access, which creates another layer of risk for intrusion into the system.

Weak Configuration/Lack of Encryption: depending on the nature of the space system and communication infrastructure and protocols employed, there is a high potential for interception. This is particularly the case for systems relying on radio frequency signals, which may lack encryption or use a low-grade one, heightening the risk of unauthorised access and collection of transmitted information. Bear in mind that the very same communication channels are used for transmitting software updates and operational commands.

Human Error: with space systems having a high degree of human interaction, there are increased risks of unintentional data leaks, system misconfigurations, and insider threats.

Sophisticated Cyber Attacks: with space systems serving an interconnected web of services and industries, there is an increased risk of nation-state actors and APT groups, which may attempt to gain unauthorized access and exfiltrate data or disrupt critical systems and could affect

Given the evolving threat landscape of the space domain, security experts and domain-specific professionals need to capitalise on validated tools and frameworks for getting informed decision on the implementation of cybersecurity controls. As part of this work and in the frame of [1], ENISA offers an open-source “Controls-to-Threats Mapping” interactive tool [13] to aid experts navigate through mazelike regulations, international frameworks, best practices, and national guidelines, as an all-encompassing tool. The tool aims to assist cybersecurity analysts identify clear and actionable recommendations for securing space systems through a thorough mapping of controls. More specifically, each control is mapped to identified threats and applied across relevant lifecycle phases.

An instance of the interactive tool is illustrated in Figure 2, where for each phase of the satellite lifecycle the tool maps the available controls to the corresponding Risk Management Framework. Built for versatility, more views and mapping variations are provided by the tool to enable experts navigate and pinpoint the proper control that fits to the nature of the incident that needs to be tackled or the space mission at hand. Overall, as indicated in Table I, 281 controls of 13 frameworks under 18 control clusters are considered by the tool, covering all the 7 phases of the satellites’ lifecycle, addressing 58 different threats.

Apart from tools, recommendations and proactive measures are essential to mitigate risks and enhance satellite security. At the EU level, NIS 2 is now at the forefront. Satellite operators must comply with it, which mandates incident reporting to facilitate information sharing and improve response strategies. *TABLE II* elaborates on the applicability of NIS 2 risk management measures (Art. 21) and reporting obligations (Art. 23) in the space domain, while in parallel it provides a mapping with the control clusters of our tool.

In addition, the Directorate-General for Defence

Controls by Lifecycle phase and Reference frameworks

Controls by cluster and segment

FIGURE 2 - INSTANCE OF “CONTROLS-TO-THREATS MAPPING” INTERACTIVE TOOL

constellations of satellites operating in synergy.

6. Risk Management And Recommendations

Industry and Space (DG-DEFIS) is the European Commission’s department tasked with developing and enforcing the regulatory frameworks that govern space activities within the EU while actively supporting the growth and competitiveness of the European space industry.

As aforementioned, complex supply chains exist in the space domain, implying the need for continuous monitoring of suppliers to prevent vulnerabilities, while thorough analysis and testing should be conducted to avoid blindly trusting and integrating commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) solutions. Furthermore, integrating security-by-design principles from the outset is crucial.

Leveraging lessons learned from other critical sectors can strengthen satellite security. Best practices include implementing cryptographic mechanisms that offer crypto agility (e.g., hybrid Post Quantum Cryptography systems⁸) in alignment with aspiring technologies of the future where satellites will play a role, such as Quantum Secure Communication in Space based on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD)⁹. Security measures such as network segmentation, thorough patch testing, system hardening, and a zero-trust approach are vital to minimizing risks.

Finally, adopting rigorous cybersecurity hygiene practices across all satellite operations will enhance resilience against cyber threats stemming from human factors. By prioritizing these strategies, the space sector can safeguard its infrastructure and ensure the continued security and reliability of satellite-based services.

TABLE I
REFERENCE FRAMEWORKS AND CONTROLS
CONSIDERED IN THE ENISA TOOL [13]

Ref. Frameworks	#Controls	Ref. Frameworks	#Controls
SPARTA	64	NIST CSF 2.0	17
ISO27k	39	NIST IR 8270	16
BSI TR-03184	30	NASA BPG	16
NIST IR 8323r1	29	BSI Profile for Space	10
NIST IR 8401	27	METI	7
NIST IR 8411	26	UKSA CST	-
		NIS 2	-
Total: 281 out of which 125 distinct controls			

7. Conclusions

The increasing reliance on space-based assets for critical infrastructure and global connectivity demands immediate attention to cybersecurity threats. As demonstrated in this paper, satellites are vulnerable to a range of cyber threats, including state-sponsored espionage, cybercriminal activities, and operational disruptions. The growing commercialization of space, combined with legacy infrastructure and complex supply chains, further amplifies risks. Addressing these challenges requires a proactive

security-by-design approach (e.g., [5][6]), continuous threat monitoring, and adherence to international cybersecurity standards. The implementation of encryption, resilient network architectures, and supply chain security measures will be critical in mitigating future threats. Moreover, international cooperation and adherence to regulatory frameworks, such as NIS 2, is essential for establishing best practices and increasing the resilience of the space sector. As the space industry continues to evolve, cybersecurity must be an integral part of its development [4], ensuring the resilience of space systems and the security of global satellite-dependent services.

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SHORT BIOGRAPHY:

Dr. Dimitrios Papamartzivanos is a Cybersecurity Officer at the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) since 2024. With over 13 years of experience in cybersecurity across both academia and industry, he has contributed to various research and cybersecurity projects. He holds an MSc and a Ph.D. in Information & Communication Systems Security, with his research focusing on advanced machine learning methods for network intrusion detection and response systems. He has published numerous papers in international journals and conferences and has submitted patent applications in the field of adaptive intrusion detection and response systems. Dimitrios has actively participated in several EU-funded cybersecurity research projects and innovation initiatives, serving as both a research associate and a technical coordinator. His research interests include

⁸ In this context a hybrid implementation uses a combination of pre-quantum (classical) and post-quantum schemes, and the mixing of pre-shared keys into all keys established via public-key cryptography (vide ENISA "Post-Quantum Cryptography - Integration study" (2022), <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/post-quantum-cryptography-integration-study>)

⁹ https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/eu-space/research-development-and-innovation/quantum-technologies_en

security and privacy for the Internet of Things (IoT), Intrusion Detection and Response Systems, Artificial Intelligence and Bio-inspired Algorithms, Adversarial AI, and Trusted Computing.

Evangelos Rekleitis is a Cybersecurity Expert working at the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) since 2019. With over 17 years of experience in cybersecurity, he has been providing expert advice and technical assistance to the EU Member States. He specializes in risk management, capacity building, and emerging threats. Currently, he is responsible for capacity building activities, including trainings and exercises, under the Support Action program, providing cybersecurity services to NIS 2 essential sectors across EU Member States. He contributed to significant projects like the ENISA Space Cyber Threat Landscape report, publications on Security Operations Centers (SOCs), cryptography, and AI, organizes the ENISA Learning and Training (Letra) events and is supporting the biannual Cyber Europe Exercise project. Before joining ENISA, he provided cybersecurity consultancy services to critical infrastructure in the Greek and Cypriot public sectors. He holds a MSc in Advanced Computing from Imperial College London and is certified as a CISM and GIAC Security Operations Manager. He is a

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Dr. Nikolaos Tantouris is the Head of Sector Security and Infrastructure at the EU Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA). He is also a member of the Knowledge and Information Team, where he focuses on the Space Cybersecurity domain. With over 12 years of experience in both industry and academia, Nikolaos is a cybersecurity expert who has worked on various projects, including space projects, the Internet of Things, Industry 4.0, smart cities, and smart mobile. He has considerable expertise overseeing and safeguarding network systems and interconnected and smart devices. Nikolaos has authored and co-authored numerous research papers and scientific reports and is a regular presenter at various international conferences.

TABLE II NIS 2 CONTROLS/REQUIREMENTS AND THEIR APPLICABILITY IN THE SPACE DOMAIN

#	Control cluster	NIS 2 risk-management measures & obligations	Applicability of Controls in Space Domain
1	Risk management / Policies & procedures	Policies on risk analysis and information system security (Art 21 2.a)	The establishment of policies on risk analysis and information system security is both a fundamental technical requirement and a strategic necessity, enabling the systematic management of cyber risks.
2	IR / BCM/DR	Incident handling (Art 21 2.b)	Effective cyber incident handling is not just a technical necessity, but a strategic measure for safeguarding the reliability, security, and resilience of satellite-based services. Definition of incident handling playbooks is important for business continuity management.
3	IR / BCM/DR	Business continuity, such as backup management and disaster recovery, and crisis management (Art 21 2.c)	Potential service disruptions in space domain could lead to “dead” objects in orbit or significantly impair economic activities and societal functions reliant on space-based services. Business continuity and recovery plans and playbooks are imperative to ensure continuous operation considering that physical intervention after launch is limited, if not impossible.
3	Supply chain management	Supply chain security, including security-related aspects concerning the relationships between each entity and its direct suppliers or service providers (Art 21 2.d)	Supply chain risks have been highlighted as the most prominent risk category in the space domain, due to the complexity of the chains, the number of stakeholders and their interdependencies.
4	Security by design / Vulnerability management / Network security	Security in network and information systems acquisition, development and maintenance, including vulnerability handling and disclosure (Art 21 2.e)	Attacks such as hijacking, jamming and DDoS of Service have been frequently materialized in the satellite sector, while complex supply chains and the use of legacy systems introduce vulnerabilities that render satellite systems susceptible to cyberattacks. The extended use of COTS combined with the fact that physical remoteness is not an adequate countermeasure means space operators should incorporate security by design and SDLC throughout all the phases of their operations.
5	Risk management	Policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures (Art 21 2.f)	Cybersecurity and risk mitigation measures are crucial, but validation through tests and compliance audits is necessary. See Phase 2 & 3 of satellite lifecycle.
6	Capacity building	Basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training (Art 21 2.g)	Adopting rigorous cybersecurity hygiene practices can enhance resilience against cyber threats stemming from human factors (Human resources segment). Recall that untrained/reckless employees have been recognized as main threat actors.
7	Network security	Policies and procedures regarding the use of cryptography and, where appropriate, encryption (Art 21 2.h)	The rapid proliferation of small, inexpensive, and rapidly deployable satellites may result to weak/lack of encryption (due to cost and time constraints) meaning there is high potential for interception, unauthorized access and collection of transmitted information.
8	Capacity building / Access management / Asset management	Human resources security, access control policies and asset management (Art 21 2.i)	Humans participating in development activities and satellite operations, is an overarching aspect spanning across the entire lifecycle of satellites and they are inextricably linked to the security and management of mission-critical assets.
9	Access management / Network security	The use of multi-factor authentication or continuous authentication solutions, secured voice, video and text communications and secured emergency communication systems	Securing SAT-to-X communication is of paramount importance, especially safeguarding Ground-to-SAT channels as those are used for transmitting software updates and operational commands. Thus, strong authentication of entities accessing, interacting and transmitting information to satellites is

		within the entity, where appropriate (Art 21 2.j)	vital.
10	Compliance	... essential and important entities notify, without undue delay, its CSIRT or, where applicable, its competent authority... (Art. 23)	Reporting of incidents is now an obligation for satellite operators as the proliferation of satellite-based services entails to high economic and societal impact.
11	Compliance	... essential and important entities communicate, without undue delay, to the recipients of their services that are potentially affected by a significant cyber threat. (Art. 23)	Satellite-based services have a vast number of end users worldwide. Many services are privacy-sensitive, such as SAT phones and geolocation-based services. Thus, it is essential to ensure that EU users impacted by significant events (e.g., data breaches) are promptly informed and be in position to take measures.